

Quantum Mechanics and Statistical Properties of a Potential $V(x)$

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Statistical equilibrium seems to make use of the idea of a lack of knowledge i.e. equal probabilities for certain features or processes. For example, for a gas with no potential there is equal probability for a particle to be at any x point, i.e. there is a loss of knowledge about x . For a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas with two body elastic collisions there is equal probability for e_1+e_2 to create any e_i+e_j provided $e_i+e_j = e_1+e_2$. Thus there is some loss of knowledge as to the reaction products. In this note we argue that the potential $V(x)$ found in classical mechanics seems to share this classical lack of knowledge or equal probability picture. Newtonian mechanics is based on the idea of force, but for a conservative force $F(x)=-dV(x)/dx$. In other words every path between the starting point and ending point experiences the same potential energy change. We argue that there is a lack of knowledge or equal probability for any of these paths and that $V(x)$ seems to be statistical. We then consider the idea of a change in momentum at each x point being described by a statistical average i.e. $dp = \text{Integral dt } (-d/dx) \text{ Sum over } k F(k,x)$ where $V(x)=\text{Sum over } k F(k,x)$ with $F(k,x)$ being a probability. This leads to a quantum approach and includes the idea of many different paths. We argue that $F(k,x)=Vk \exp(ikx)$ and further argue that if one wishes to have $G(p+k,x)=\exp(ikx) G(p,x)$ for a quantum particle (experiencing statistically these impulse hits), then $G(p,x) = \exp(ipx)$ i.e. the wavefunction of a free quantum particle.

Statistical Features and Maximum Entropy in Classical Mechanics?

Classical mechanics is usually considered to be a deterministic theory which follows a particle in space and time i.e. $x(t)$ found by solving Newton's second law: $dp/dt = F(x)$. For a conservative force $F(x) = -dV(x)/dx$ so: $\text{Integral dx } F(x) = - \text{Integral dV/dx dx} = -V(x_f) + V(x_0)$. i.e. the change in potential energy (or the work done) is path independent and depends only on the initial and endpoint x_0 and x_f . In fact, even paths which violate Newton's law but start and end at x_0 and x_f yield the same change in potential energy. This suggests that all paths have the same probability in terms of work or that one does not have information about one path versus another. This seems to be statistical and characteristic of an equilibrium situation even though a particle moving through a potential $V(x)$ (or its 3-D counterpart) may seem to be anything but equilibrium. An equilibrium situation is associated with maximum entropy (often subject to constraints).

We note that for a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas with no potential there is equal probability for a particle to be at any x i.e. no information about any preferred x . Furthermore for a two body collision involving e_1 and e_2 any outcome for which $e_i + e_j = e_1 + e_2$ has equal probability, thus one does not have preferred knowledge about the collision outcome (except for the constraint e_1+e_2). We argue that $V(x)$ represents an equilibrium of equal probability for different paths in a similar manner.

Extending the Idea of Probability Contained in the Potential $V(x)$

As a next step, we consider extending the idea of probability found in the potential. From Newton's second law: $dp = \int dt (-dV/dx)$ i.e. an impulse. We consider a point x and imagine that dp is due to an average of impulse hits i.e a purely statistical picture:

$$dp = \int dt (-d/dx) \sum_k F(k,x) \quad ((1))$$

Furthermore, each $(-d/dx) F(k,x)$ should be the same as: $-ik F(k,x)$ ((2))

Because one wishes to have an average i.e. $dp = \int dp \sum_k (-ik) F(k,x)$. ((3))

Equating ((1)) and ((3)) suggests that: $-d/dx F(k,x) = -ik F(k,x)$ or that $F(k,x) = \exp(ikx)$ ((4)).

Spatial invariance has been taken into account in introducing i .

Thus, ((1)) becomes a traditional Fourier series, but $[\int dt \exp(ikx)]$ is interpreted as a probability of an impulse of k being delivered at x . In the above section we argued that $V(x)$ represents a kind of statistical equilibrium in terms of paths or a maximum entropy characteristic of equilibrium, so we suggest $\exp(ikx)$ may be associated with maximum entropy.

In such a case:

$$\ln(\exp(ikx)) = \text{information} = ikx \quad \text{or} \quad -id/dx \text{ information} = k \text{ the information of the impulse hit} \quad ((4))$$

Extension to a Quantum Particle

If the potential $V(x)$ is viewed as an average of impulse hits (with $V_k \exp(ikx)$ probabilities), it seems that a particle only exhibits Newton's law on average, but would receive impulse hits of k from the pieces of $V(x)$. As a result, one may suggest:

$$G(p+k, x) = \exp(ikx) G(p, x) \quad ((5))$$

For $k \rightarrow 0$ $G(p+k,x) = G(p) + kx dG/dp = (1+ikx) G(p,x)$ ((6)) (assuming $G(p,x)=G(px)$)

Then: $dG/dp = ix G$ or $G = \exp(ipx)$ ((7))

Thus, the quantum particle probability takes the form of the functional portion of the probability associated with $V(x)$. This quantum particle may have unusual motion.

It is interesting to note that for both the potential $V(x)$ and the quantum particle a complex (imaginary) probability arises in contrast with probabilities used in classical statistical mechanics which are real. In previous notes we have argued that this is due to the fact that the momentum of the quantum particle and even that of the potential $V(x)$ are not discernible while the particle is interacting. For the quantum particle, its momentum is continuously changing due to impulse hits which interfere or blend to form $V(x)$. It is $V(x)$ which is seen by experiment, not the impulse hits. In order to see a p momentum state of the quantum particle, it needs to undergo an interaction with a probe which may measure its momentum, but completely disrupts or breaks its interaction with $V(x)$. (These ideas also apply to a quantum bound state and lead to a particle's momentum being measured if it is knocked out of the bound state, or its wave type behaviour within the potential measured from $W(x)W(x)$, where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction).

For a bound state one combines probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ to form the ensemble $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx)$ with $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx) / W(x)$.

Statistical Considerations

Like with the potential, $-id/dx \ln(\exp(ipx)) = p$ i.e. d/dx information = p momentum information.

In classical statistical problems one usually maximizes entropy with respect to various constraints. The constraint in the quantum problem is that average kinetic energy + $V(x)$ at each x point equal E (energy) for a bound state problem i.e.

$$-1/2m \ d/dx \ d/dx \ W + V(x) \ W = E \ W \quad ((8))$$

It seems that entropy does enter into ((8)) because one may note that $-1/2m \ d/dx \ d/dx \ W$ is of a very special form for the kinetic energy. We have argued above that $\exp(ipx)$ is already associated with a kind of maximum entropy in $V(x)$ (which treats all paths with endpoints x_0 and x_f as receiving the same potential energy). This dictates the form $\exp(ipx)$ for a particle in a state of momentum p . The constraint equation ((8)) governs the weights of the ensemble created from $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$. This is not the usual manner of maximizing entropy subject to constraints for which maximization occurs for the "whole scenario" including an entropy expression with constraints together. Furthermore, the idea of a maximum entropy for a free p probability is applied to a state which is not even discernible in the usual classical manner for which a probability must be real.

This seems to suggest that it is the form of each impulse hit from $V(x)$ and each free state of a quantum particle which must conform to a maximum entropy condition. After that, conservation of energy is enough to fix the weights $a(p)$ in $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$.

In classical statistical mechanics, a free particle moves with momentum p for the case of no potential. The concept of maximizing entropy subject to energy constraints, which is equivalent to reaction balance [$f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$ with $e_1+e_2 = e_3+e_4$] applies to collisions. In quantum mechanics there is already a probability associated with impulse hits in $V(x)$ which must comply with $F(x)=-dV/dx$ and probability combinations when a quantum particle with momentum p receives an impulse. Thus maximization of entropy applies to the impulse collision of a single p state quantum particle with a single k impulse of the potential to obtain a

maximized free particle probability $\exp(ipx)$. The formation of average energy values i.e. ((8)) is not restricted by maximization of entropy because each $\exp(ipx)$ and $V_k \exp(ikx)$ hit already maximizes entropy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the ideas of statistical equilibrium i.e. maximum entropy seem to be present in the classical mechanical potential $V(x)$ because $F(x) = -dV/dx$ implies that all paths between x_0 and x_f receive the same change in potential energy. In other words, all paths have the same probability and there is no information about a preferred path. This even applies to non-classical paths. As a result we try to view $V(x)$ in terms of a probabilistic average of impulse hits such that: $F(x) = \text{Sum over } k \text{ } k \text{ Impulse probability} = -dV/dx$ leads to $k * \text{Impulse probability} = -d \text{ impulse probability} / dx$ or $\text{impulse probability} = V_k \exp(ikx)$ (or $\exp(-ikx)$) if one wishes to have spatial invariance. Thus, $V(x)$ appears as an interfering (superposition) average of impulses, meaning they are not discernible in the usual classical manner. This impacts a quantum particle if one wishes to have its probability satisfy: $G(p+k,x) = \exp(ikx) G(p,x)$ leading to $G(p,x) = \exp(ipx)$. It may be noted that one examines an impulse k of a potential and a quantum particle with momentum p and so "maximization of entropy" applies to this specific type of collision and not an entire scenario of a probability distribution which conserves energy. In other words an impulse from the potential leads to a momentum change p to $p+k$ without any constraints in the quantum particle (except for the idea of spatial invariance which follows automatically). To deal with a particle in a bound state, one creates an ensemble of maximum entropy free particle probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) \exp(ipx)$ such that $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ and applies conservation of energy at each point to this ensemble which already contains maximum entropy probabilities (for impulses).